

CAST STAINED-GLASS WINDOWS IN A MAGNIFICENT PAINTING

Obidov Bakhtiyor Saifullaevich

Senior teacher of the ""Majestic painting"" department of the National Institute of Painting and Design named after Kamoliddin Behzod
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Annotation: In this article, the role of cast stained glass in a magnificent painting, the main features of cast stained glass, its historical antiquity, secrets of methodology and consumption, mutual relations, and the original historical directions of stained glass are fully described.

Key words: charming painting, cast stained glass, aesthetic features, color image.

Introduction:

Cast stained glass is a type of stained glass that is made of plastic in red, black, yellow, green and other colors. This method allows you to create images using toys or mirrors.

Cast stained glass is usually placed in the upper part of the windows in the majestic painting. Through these stained glass windows, it is possible to create colorful compositions and depict images. These image types include toys, figures, animals, nature scenes, and more. The main features of cast stained glass in a majestic painting are to allow images to be transformed into a colorful composition and create a visible, natural and attractive feeling.

Literature analysis and methodology:

The role of cast stained glass in majestic painting is widely used in order to create a benevolent atmosphere among people, to add decorativeness and to help beautify developing areas. Cast stained glass in majestic color is a type of decorative art that has been popularized abroad in the field of art and architecture, and has gained interest in studying the secrets of its consumption. The art of Uzbekistan throughout its history is defined by a unique and visible male identity. This characteristic represents both physical and spiritual characteristics for each type of self-art. However, there is also an art form that has a completely different effect in several works.

Cast stained glass is one of the most modern and elegant art forms of Uzbekistan. Using this method, stylized plastic images are created, which can be obtained in red and reddish-black retail, black, yellow, green and other colors of colored plastic. These stained glass windows are usually located on the top of the windows and are designed with their tracks or toys.

Results:

This stained glass method includes different colors and compositions in a way that is characteristic of the installation of the image. In the majestic painting, cast stained glass is used to depict the edges of windows, figures, animals, natural scenes, etc. These stained glass windows are usually created to help people overcome unhappiness, adversity, depression, and energy gaps.

In addition, the role of cast stained glass in a majestic painting combines decorativeness and creativity in a unique way. Its natural colors and attractive image type are symbols of

escape from misfortune and bullies in the viewers and play an important role in changing the general atmosphere.

Cast stained glass is an ancient art form since the Middle Ages, which has its own unique and meaningful style of decoration. The main feature of this art is that it allows you to create a colorful image based on meanings using colored plastic red and black retail.

Discussion:

Cast stained glass in a majestic painting is actually plastic colored elements located on the top of the windows. They are made of plastics melted at room temperature and processed with cold and non-moistened pens. These stained glass windows are usually used as decorative elements for windows, streets, mosques, restaurants, and other public places.

The role of stained glass in a majestic painting is important in expressing additional meanings acquired by people, creating a natural, dynamic and visible image. His colorful images show constant changes with the light coming through the glass, and have dignified feelings and meanings, enhancing human connections.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it can be said that the role of cast stained glass in the majestic painting is related to the display of Uzbek national art and values, historical and cultural gardens. This art form is one of the products of Uzbekistan that has gained international recognition and has raised its name around the world. Thus, the place of cast stained glass in the magnificent painting is the ancient art of Uzbekistan, which represents the elegant and completely different images of the stylistic plastic art, which is recognized and appreciated at the international level with its historical, cultural and aesthetic characteristics

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